

RRI in the context of Anthropocene: a systems analysis.

RRI emerged in response to what is called 'big challenges', complex systemic crises at a global scale. So in contrast to classical R&I which is highly specialised, RRI should adopt a broad systemic approach taking the planetary ecosystem (thermodynamic laws) as its frame of reference. Scientists agree that human activity is the root cause of today's crises (Anthropocene), so RRI should help us to understand what drives this disruptive human activity. In line with research on the sustainability of complex dynamic flow systems, RRI has to foster resilience by detecting and upscaling alternative approaches. Many citizens and CSO's today develop innovative socioeconomic practices, pursuing the common good in community based 'living (or urban) labs'. Companies confronted with the effect of the big crises are exploring new business models and partnerships (e.g. ethical business, circular economy etc.) RRI has to clarify what makes these initiatives resilient and under what conditions their impact can be heightened so as to guarantee a timely regime shift. The hypothesis is that this requires specific infrastructure, partnerships and methodologies, supported by innovative R&I policies.

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